

Too risky - risk analysis as a decision making tool for the safe design of long railway tunnels

Introduction

RAILWAYS throughout Europe are experiencing a period of development and investment.

Ambitious programmes have been undertaken in Denmark, France, Germany, Great Britain, Italy and Switzerland, where High Speed Railway (HSR) Systems and challenging tunnel links such as the EuroChannel, the Great Belt, the Brenner tunnel and the otschberg and Gotthard basis tunnels have been realised or are currently under development or design.

High train speeds and the presence of long tunnels have highlighted the problem of safe transportation, since accidents may now cause extremely severe consequences.

In this note we focus on the role of risk analysis techniques as an aid to conventional design activities, for the safe design of long railway tunnels.

Such techniques have been successfully used for projects such as the tunnels of the High Speed Railway Lines in Germany (Basler & Hoffmann, Ernst

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Basler & Partner, 1983), the Great Belt Link in Denmark (Rasmussen and Gudum, 1992), four new tunnels along the existing Brenner line (Lagasco et al., 1992) and the new Brenner tunnel.

Objectives

The main objectives of a risk analysis applied to underground transportation systems may be summarised as follows:

- to identify and to analyse the most significant hazard scenarios with respect to damages to passengers, environment and facilities;

- to select and define, on the basis of cost/benefit considerations, the most appropriate safety measures, these being managerial measures, (e.g. emergency procedures) infrastructural measures (e.g. escape ways' geometry) and safety systems (e.g. ventilation system, fire and gas detection systems, etc.);

- to validate the proposed solutions by computing the overall risk level and by comparing it to predefined target safety levels.

Table 1 below shows, for different recent tunnels, selected design characteristics which enter in the risk analysis validation.

Methodology

To fulfil the aforementioned objectives, a complete risk analysis would be based on the activities shown below in Figure 1. Using the basic tunnel design and referring to historical railway accidents, a first screening of possible accident scenarios, as listed below, is performed:

- Internal events such as:
 - derailment
 - collision
 - fire and smoke

Table 1: Comparison of relevant safety parameters

Tunnel	Tunnel System	Length (km)	Distance Interconn. (m)	Width of pavement (m)	Traffic (Tr./Day)	Goods Train (%)	Max. Vel. (km/h)
Landruken	ODTT	10.8	-	1.60	240	60	250
Prato Tires-P.te Gardena	ODTT	13.5	-	1.40	170	45	160
Great Belt Link	TSTT	8.0	250	1.20	240	40	100
Eurotunnel	TSTT + ST	50	375	1.10	110	45	160
Seikan	TSTT	53.9	600-1000	0.- 0.6	40	50	240
Gotthard Feas. St. 1992	TSTT + SR	≈ 50	500	0.75	360	65	200
Brenner Feas. Study 1987	ODTT + ST	≈ 58	250	1.60	340	80	250

Legend: ODTT = One double track tunnel
 TSTT = Two single track tunnels
 ST = Service Tunnel
 SR = Safety Rooms

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- release and/or explosion of hazardous substances

- loss of traction power

● External events such as:

- earthquakes

- landslides

- flooding

● Human actions or errors such as:

- operation faults

- erroneous maintenance

- terrorist attacks and sabotage

For each accident scenario a probabilistic analysis is performed to evaluate the probability of the initiating event occurring and the possible scenarios that may result. Two steps of analysis are required:

● statistical evaluation of the probability of occurrence of the initiating events.

● development and probabilistic analysis of fault and event trees set up to model possible scenarios resulting from the initiating event.

The influence of the safety measures is explicitly considered in the event tree analysis.

For each accident scenarios, consequences in terms of damage to passengers, environment and facilities are evaluated. These analyses are based on sophisticated tools which involve the modelling of relevant accident scenarios in a confined environment.

Safety measures are analysed by evaluating the actual performance of each one:

● For the infrastructural measures:

- To verify how the geometry of the escape ways influences evacuation times and mortality in the case of fire and smoke.

- To verify whether cable protections and other facilities will withstand heat loads in the event of fire.

- To verify whether the structural elements will withstand impact loads in the event of derailment.

● For the safety systems:

- To study the effect of the ventilation system as a mitigative measure in the event of fire, smoke or release of poisonous gases.

- To assess the reliability of the various safety systems which may fail to operate in emergencies. Such an assessment

Figure 1: Risk analysis process flow

Figure 2: Block diagram for possible scenarios given an initiating event (derailment)

may be performed qualitatively (eg via Failure Modes and Effects Analysis) or quantitatively (eg via operability analysis and fault tree analysis).

The global risk may be calculated for various alternative configurations of the systems. Cost factors must also be taken into account so allowing the selection of the most effective solution, effectively maximising safety and minimising costs.

Risk Evaluation and Risk Appraisal

The following representative results are based on a critical review of railway accidents in Western Europe during the last twenty years and on several risk analyses.

Influence of Tunnel Configuration

The influence of tunnel configuration on risk is significant. For example, the TSTT (Two Single Track Tunnels) system is safer than a ODTT (One Double Track Tunnel) system as collision accident probability is reduced and the involvement of a second train after derailment is improbable.

Figure 2 shows the approximate relative risk value for possible tunnel configurations for long tunnels (over 10 Kilometres). The values are indicative, based on several risk studies, but can be changed by the implementation of safety measures.

Influence of Safety Measures

Safety measures can be classified in the following groups:

- Prevention measures
- Mitigation measures
- Measures improving self rescue and assisted rescue.

The analyses have shown that safety measures can drastically reduce risk up to a factor of approximately two.

The final design of the safety systems is based on cost-benefit considerations. By such analyses it can be shown that costly rescue trains are not appropriated.

In the context of risk appraisal quantitative safety criteria must be defined to determine whether a given risk is acceptable or unacceptable. Existing railway regulations and codes do not address the problem of quantitative safety criteria, but provide only recommendations.

Conclusions

The treatment of safety aspects in long railway tunnels is of significant importance. Risk analysis can be used as a decision tool for:

- selection of tunnel configuration
- evaluation of overall risk of the HSR (High Speed Railway) system
- definition of an optimal package of safety measures
- improvement of the current safety criteria in railway standards.

A look into the fire resistance of road tunnels

Abstract

THIS paper demonstrates the use of technical analysis for the safe design of fire resistance in road tunnels.

The technical analysis is presented within a safe design strategy enabling decisions on the optimal package of measures to be made on the basis of "tolerable" damage. The analysis is illustrated by way of an example.

Nomenclature

- Cf BS 476 correction factor (-)
- f flame elongation factor (-)
- hs fire source height (m)
- ht tunnel height (m)
- lo flame length in open air (m)
- lt flame length in tunnel (m)
- Tb BS 476 temperature (°C)
- Th hydrocarbon temperature (°C)

Introduction

Serious fires in tunnels causing considerable damage and requiring costly and disruptive repairs have been reported in North America, Europe and Japan (Haack, 1992).

For example, the Nihonzaka Tunnel fire in 1979 incurred loss and damage of more than US \$25 million.

An increasing emphasis is being placed by regulatory authorities on ensuring that reasonable fire resistance is achieved in tunnels.

Swart (1990) showed that it would cost more than US \$5 million to install safety facilities for an existing tunnel in the Netherlands. It is apparent that whilst expensive measures could provide protection against the fire, it is necessary to ensure that the measures are both practicable and effective.

Objectives

Because of the rarity of major fire incidents in road tunnels, the accident statistics do not provide an adequate basis on which to determine the fire resistance requirements.

Both laboratory and full scale fire tests in tunnels are being carried out (Haack, 1992) to examine fire resistance of specific tunnel construction materials. The applicability of the results to other materials is however uncertain.

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Furthermore, most of the current tunnel design procedures involve prescriptive rules and criteria (eg. PIARC, 1991) which do not allow much flexibility or innovation.

To improve the situation, this paper presents an analytical methodology for carrying out design calculations. The analysis is demonstrated for a hydrocarbon fire in a proposed road tunnel.

Safe Design Strategy

Tunnel schemes are required to define for all probable situations an optimal package of measures to reduce the effects of a fire.

The optimal measures cannot be based solely on technical data and costs have to be determined for each situation.

Questions such as: "Are the fire effects tolerable, acceptable, or negligible, or do they require measures which are reasonably practicable, raise social, political, or legal issues" (Cassidy, 1992).

Standard fire resistance measures are therefore unlikely to apply universally to all probable situations. Increasingly, decision makers find it useful to approach safe tunnel design on the basis of "tolerable" damage.

What constitutes tolerable damage varies with the fire scenario, depending on its likely frequency of occurrence, the cost of the damage, both due to the repair work and to the disruption, and the cost of design improvements.

The safe design strategy is illustrated in Figure 1. Below, the technical analysis is outlined.

Technical Analysis

Standard methods for fire source, flame characteristics and heat transfer have been employed here. Since many of these have been developed for open, non-tunnel environments, they have in some cases had to be adapted to become